

Travel Package Management System

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Abstract. The Travel Package Management System is a comprehensive web-based platform designed to simplify and streamline the management of tourism services for both administrators and travelers. This system allows travel agencies to efficiently create, organize, and manage various tour packages that include components such as transportation, accommodation, and dining options. Users can browse available packages, view detailed itineraries, select custom options (like hotels and restaurants), and purchase trips with transparent pricing that updates in real-time based on their selections and travel duration.

Keywords: admin controls, content management, dynamic pricing, payment processing, secure booking.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry has experienced rapid growth in recent years, with increasing demand for seamless and customized travel experiences. As a result, travel agencies and tour operators are shifting from traditional purchase methods to digital platforms to better manage their services and meet customer expectations. The system also supports user authentication, profile management, and purchased history tracking, ensuring a seamless and personalized travel planning experience. Designed with scalability and user experience in mind, the Travel Package Management System enhances operational efficiency for agencies while providing a smooth and intuitive purchase journey for travelers.

PROBLEM

This system is very convenient for young travelers, newlywed couples, solo adventurers, and families who are unsure about how to plan, organize, or manage their travel experiences effectively. A relaxing and enjoyable vacation is undoubtedly the most popular among the very efficient travelers. Traveling to new destinations offers valuable experiences and personal growth. A well-organized trip is essential for ensuring convenience and creating lasting memories. For this reason, travelers should carefully select appropriate travel packages and be mindful of travel regulations and safety measures. Travel package Management System is very efficient for tourists and travel planners. The users can get accurate and updated information about various travel destinations from this system. In addition, the users can easily access information about the challenges faced by travelers and recommended solutions in today's travel environment.

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APPROACH

This system consists of two roles: Admin and User. On the user side, if the user does not have an account, he or she must register. If the user has already registered, the user can proceed to log in. After logging in, the user can access home page, view announcement, about us, contact us, packages, notification, manage profile and check purchased history. The users select a full package or a customized package. After choosing a package, the user proceeds to submit purchase. The users can view confirm or cancel in notification. Then they can view receipt. After that the users can log out and the system will stop working.

On the admin side, the admin enters login credentials. If it is invalid, the system loops back to the login screen. If it is valid, the admin gains access to the dashboard and functionalities. After successfully logging in, the admin can manage account, view dashboard, manage user list, manage customized package lists, manage full package lists, car lists, hotel lists, purchase requests, incomes and check notification. After that the admin can log out and the system will stop working.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) utilizes data modeling techniques to define business processes and lay the groundwork for a relational database structure. In the ERD, attributes can be designated as primary keys, which uniquely identify each record, or as foreign keys, which link related attributes across different entities. Additionally, cardinality notation is used to specify the nature and constraints of relationships between entities. In the database, there are nine data tables. The tables are users, purchase, packages, cars, hotels, restaurants, full_packages, full_package_purchase and user_notifications. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

Each page of the Travel Package Management System is designed with user convenience in mind and follows a clean and intuitive layout using Bootstrap. The system ensures a user-friendly experience for both visitors and registered users. The visitors can browse available full and customized packages, view destination images, descriptions, and pricing, access homepage, announcement, about us, contact. All these features are available without requiring login, ensuring easy access to information for all visitors. The user can view and update personal profile, customize packages by selecting cars, hotels, restaurants, and activities, purchase packages with desired dates, durations, and guest counts, upload payment slips and choose payment methods (e.g, WavePay, KPay, AYA Pay), view purchased history

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and receive notifications. This system serves as a digital travel assistant, eliminating the need for manual purchases and long wait times. It allows the users to plan their trips efficiently using any internet-connected device. This system acts as a central hub that allows users to manage their travel plans without physically visiting the travel agency, offering convenience and real-time access to information and services.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The Travel Package Management System offers a digital solution that integrates key travel services into one platform, improving efficiency for administrators and providing a smooth experience for users. It supports features like customizable packages, secure purchase, and real-time pricing, bridging the gap between service providers and customers. By replacing traditional purchase methods, the system enhances service delivery, boosts customer satisfaction, and has strong potential for future expansion in the tourism industry.

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